

Investigation on transport properties under extreme conditions of hydrostatic pressure and magnetic field on $\text{Nd}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.4$)

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Abstract:

We investigate the temperature dependence of the electrical resistivity and field dependence of magneto resistance of $\text{Nd}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.4$) perovskite manganites. Figure 1 (a) and (b) show that electrical resistivity measurements in the temperature range 50 – 300 K at ambient pressure and 1 GPa hydrostatic pressure respectively which indicate metal- insulator transition at 90 K and 97 K in the cooling cycles and 107 K and 115 K in the warming cycles at ambient pressure and 1 GPa hydrostatic pressure respectively. When the pressure increases at 1 GPa, the metal-insulator transition (T_{MI}) temperature which shift to higher temperature. We investigate that the magneto resistance (MR) of the material in the temperature interval $\Delta T = 5\text{K}$ at magnetic field (-5T to +5T) under ambient and hydrostatic pressure 1GPa. The negative magneto resistance has decreased by applying pressure at 1GPa. Pressure increases the T_{MI} metal-insulator transition temperature and decrease the negative magneto resistance value.

FIG. 1. (a) and (b) Temperature dependence resistivity of $\text{Nd}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.4$) at ambient and 1GPa hydrostatic pressure respectively, (c) and (d) field dependence of magneto resistance (MR) of $\text{Nd}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.4$) in the temperature interval $\Delta T = 5\text{K}$ at magnetic field (-5T to +5T) under ambient and hydrostatic pressure 1GPa respectively.